

Treatment ^b	Iron content (ppm)				Manganese content (ppm)				Rice yield (g/pot, 6 plants)	
	NH ₄ OAc, pH 4.8		NH ₄ OAc, pH 3.0		Exch. Mn NH ₄ OAc, pH 7		Reducible Mn NH ₄ OAc, pH 7 + 0.2% hydroquinone		Grain	Straw
	8d	15 d	8d	15 d	8d	15 d	8d	15 d		
Cal, FYM, Dry	2.5	2.5	4.1	4.1	1.0	1.0	290	290	7.65	36.80
Cal, FYM, Sat	5.7	7.5	7.4	19.6	7.0	10.5	277	270	12.25	47.60
Cal, FYM, Subm	7.0	9.2	24.7	36.5	9.5	15.0	266	252	19.47	56.00
Cal, no FYM, Dry	2.5	2.5	4.1	4.1	1.0	1.0	290	290	3.85	33.30
Cal, no FYM, Sat	3.7	6.0	7.9	13.6	3.2	7.7	282	277	8.93	44.60
Cal, no FYM, Subm	6.2	8.0	21.4	25.2	4.7	12.1	277	257	16.42	50.60
Noncal, FYM, Dry	4.0	4.0	5.9	5.9	1.8	1.8	312	312	8.15	38.20
Noncal, FYM, Sat	6.2	10.2	19.3	21.2	9.5	14.5	297	287	15.00	47.40
Noncal, FYM, Subm	7.2	10.3	46.9	52.0	13.0	19.0	287	277	20.90	59.40
Noncal, no FYM, Dry	4.0	4.0	5.9	5.9	1.8	1.8	312	312	7.12	37.40
Noncal, no FYM, Sat	5.0	8.7	17.9	17.9	5.0	10.5	303	285	9.60	41.00
Noncal, no FYM, Subm	7.0	9.5	26.7	36.0	8.1	15.5	292	280	15.85	48.90

^a Mean of 2 replications. ^b Cal= calcareous, FYM = farmyard manure, Sat = saturated, Subm = submerged.

sowing moisture from dry to submergence, and with the duration of moisture treatment (see table). Soil saturation and submergence 15 days before sowing resulted in a greater release of exchangeable Fe and Mn, which might be due to reduced conditions (Eh reduced from 530 to 260 mV in calcareous soil and from 510 to 256 mV in noncalcareous soil) and decrease in pH (from 8.2 to 7.6 in calcareous soil and from 8.1 to 7.8 in noncalcareous soil). Noncalcareous soil

recorded higher exchangeable Fe and Mn than calcareous soil. The addition of farmyard manure resulted in higher content of exchangeable Fe and Mn. The highest exchangeable Fe and Mn were observed under the presowing soil submergence treatment with farmyard manure.

Easily reducible Mn, however, showed a reverse trend. It rapidly decreased as a result of presowing moisture regimes with the addition of farm-

yard manure, which was accompanied by an increase in exchangeable Mn.

An increase in rice grain and straw yield was observed. It probably was due to an increase in the supply of Fe and Mn in the soil as a result of soil water treatments 15 days before sowing. The highest grain and straw yield was obtained in noncalcareous soil under presowing submergence treatment with addition of farmyard manure. ■

Population of the weed *Marsilia quartrifoliata* in plots with azolla

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Irrigation water is usually released from Mattur reservoir in June in Thanjavur district. The first short-duration crop in the double-crop wetland system is planted in June-July. In the single-cropped wetland area, long-duration varieties are planted in September-October, 2-3 months after water is released. Submergence of those fields during that period encourages some wetland weeds such as *Marsilia quartrifoliata*, *Panicum repens*, *P. colonum*, *Cyperus rotundus*, *Pistia striotus*, and *Echinochloa colona*. *M. quartrifoliata* spreads quickly and manual labor to remove it from the field before planting costs US\$41-103/ha.

At PES, fields where azolla was growing differed in *Marsilia* weed population from fields with no azolla. Weed population was assessed in 10 randomly selected areas, 10 m² each, in which azolla grew densely and in which azolla was absent. The weights follow:

Plots	Mean fresh weed wt (kg/10 m ²)
With dense azolla growth	0.52
Control (no azolla)	26.31

Trials on seed requirements showed that a minimum of 1 t seed material/ha was needed for the samba fields. Azolla can be grown without phosphorus application if the old water is drained from the field once a week and fresh water is maintained at 5-10 cm.

Thus a thick layer of azolla can ward off *M. quartrifoliata* while saving 25 kg N/ha, as previously reported. ■

Azolla manuring rectifies zinc deficiency

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Zinc deficiency is a problem in the second crop (thaladi) immediately following the first crop (kuruvai) in double-cropped wetlands in Thanjavur district of Tamil Nadu.

A trial with three replications during the 1979-80 thaladi season studied the maximum level of azolla (*A. pinnata*) application that gave a significant additional yield in the variety ADT31. The number of leaves and the intensity of leaf area affected by zinc deficiency were assessed 4 times — 20th, 25th, 30th, and 35th day after transplanting (DT) — as the zinc deficiency was observed in a severe form in the early stages of crop growth. The mean of the maximum

Data on zinc deficiency symptoms.^a Aduthurai, India.

Treatment	% of leaves affected		Intensity of leaf area affected (%)	
	AV	TV	AV	TV
Control	67.3	55.1	31.2	34.0
Azolla 10 t/ha	42.0	40.4	12.3	20.5
" 20 "	17.5	24.7	5.9	14.1
" 30 "	8.7	17.2	2.0	8.1
" 40 "	3.1	10.1	0.7	4.8
" 50 "	0.5	4.1	0.5	4.1
" 60 "	0.5	4.1	0.5	4.1
" 70 "	0.5	4.1	0.5	4.1
" 80 "	0.5	4.1	0.5	4.1
" 90 "	0.5	4.1	0.5	4.1
" 100 "	0.5	4.1	0.5	4.1
C.D. (P= 0.05%)		6.3	4.7	

^aAV = actual value of zinc deficiency worked out in percentage; TV = transformed value (angular value) of the percentage of zinc deficiency. Intensity of leaf areas affected = the area of the leaf covered by zinc deficiency symptoms.

deficiency symptom on the 25th DT for each treatment was recorded (see table).

Significant reduction in zinc deficiency was observed with azolla application from 10 t/ha onward compared to the untreated control. The deficiency

symptom was negligible at 40 t azolla/ ha and the crop was completely free from it at 50 t/ha and above. ■

Comparison of supergranules, sulfur-coated and ordinary urea in transplanted Jaya rice

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A field experiment compared the effectiveness of urea supergranules, sulfur-coated urea (SCU), and ordinary urea at low to moderate levels of nitrogen application (see table). At 30 kg N/ ha, the supergranules proved significantly superior to the best split of ordinary urea but statistically at par with SCU. At higher levels of nitrogen application (60 and 90 kg N/ha), supergranules and SCU were not superior to the best split, but were definitely superior to single basal incorporation. ■

Effects of urea supergranules, sulfur-coated urea (SCU), and ordinary urea on transplanted Jaya rice, Pantnagar, India, 1980 rainy season.^a

Nitrogen rate (kgN/ha)	Source and method of application ^b	Grain yield (t/ha)
0	No nitrogen	2.5
30	Urea, best split	3.6
30	SCU, broadcast and incorporated, basal	4.1
30	Supergranules of urea, placed ^a 10-12 cm deep	4.3
60	Urea, best split	5.2
60	Urea, broadcast and incorporated, basal	4.2
60	SCU, broadcast and incorporated, basal	5.1
60	Supergranules of urea, placed 10-12 cm deep	5.3
90	Urea, best split	5.8
90	Urea, broadcast and incorporated, basal	4.3
90	SCU, broadcast and incorporated, basal	5.7
90	Supergranules of urea, placed 10-12 cm deep	5.7
		S.Em. ± 220
		C.D. (5%) 640
		C.V.(%) 9

^aNursery sowing: June. ^bPlacement was in the center of 4 hills.

Environment and its influence

A simple screening technique to identify rice genotypes with low photorespiration

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C₃ and C₄ plants are known to differ sharply in their response to physical factors such as light, temperature, and oxygen concentration. Physical conditions largely govern the efficiency of the physiological and biochemical parameters that control the growth processes. Adverse physical stresses such as high temperature, light intensity, or oxygen concentration enhance photorespiration and impose a premium on net photosynthetic efficiency for productivity in C₃ plants.

Gangadharan and Kleinhofs have used those stress parameters in a screen-

ing technique to isolate barley and wheat genotypes that are more efficient in net photosynthesis. Only the two stress parameters oxygen and light are now used for rice.

A plexiglass chamber, 1.5 × 0.6 × 0.6 m was placed on a zinc tray filled with water, with outlet and inlet. A measured quantity of oxygen was let in daily for about 10 minutes through a flowmeter at 2 liters/ minute from an oxygen cylinder after the chamber was filled with atmospheric air so that the enriched air had an oxygen concentration of 25-26%. A mercury light continuously lighted the chamber at night to give a light intensity of 25-26 klux. A thermometer held through the ceiling of the chamber recorded temperature. Earthen pots, 10 cm in diameter, with 10 seedlings (aged 15-20 days) each, were kept on the tray in water. Four pots of maize seedlings were also dis-

tributed as checks for screening.

The seedlings turned pale and chlorotic after about 10 days and withered completely within 4 weeks. Some plants survived comparatively longer than others under high oxygen concentration. Data on seedling survival and photosynthetic rates after flowering and 3 days after oxygen enrichment in the chamber are in the table. Two runs were made on sets showing survival.

The preliminary observations clearly established variations in the rice genotypes' ability to withstand higher oxygen concentration under continuous light. These observations are relevant in that higher levels of oxygen inhibit the activity of the carboxylating enzyme (RuDP-carboxylase) and enhance RuDP oxygenase activity. Obviously photorespiration was enhanced under high oxygen levels. Genotypes with low oxygenase activity even at high oxygen level